

EFFICACY OF HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINES IN MYOPIA CONTROL USING BOGER BOENNINGHAUSEN'S CHARECTERISTIC REPERTORY IN A CONSTITUTIONAL WAY

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ABSTRACT

Background: Myopia is a refractive error in which parallel rays of light coming from infinity are focused in front of the retina when accommodation remains at rest. Myopia has emerged as one of the crucial public health problems in the urban population of India. The prevalence of myopia varies with different factors. It is one of the major cause of the visual impairment in the developed and in the developing world. **Aim:** To evaluate the efficacy of Homoeopathic medicines for reducing and arresting the present refractive error of myopia. **Design:** This is a prospective, experimental, longitudinal, non – randomized, single blinded, clinical study. **Methods:** This study on myopia was performed on a sample size of 40, age group of 7-30 years with a duration of almost 6months. After the screening process, the selected patients went through optometric evaluation followed by a

proper case taking with the best suitable homoeopathic medicines. Based on the individualisation and called for subsequent visits for five more times. In every visit each of them were assessed by Likert scale. **Result:** After 6 months of the study, although significant changes were seen in each case as per Likert scale scoring for subjective symptoms, no significant changes in degree of myopia were observed clinically. **Conclusion:** Although the

result was statistically significant in showing that there was a control in myopia progression, but for getting a firm conclusion of the same, this study needs to be carried out for longer duration.

KEYWORDS: Constitutional remedies, Homoeopathy, Repertory, Optometry, Myopia, Retinoscopy.

INTRODUCTION

Myopia is regarded as one of the very commonest cause of visual impairment now a days all over world.^[1,2] Myopia is the word which has been derived from the exact word “muopia” which is basically a Greek word and it means to close the eyes. Myopia is a kind of anomaly related to refraction where conjugate focus of the retina is in front of the eye, provided the eye is not accommodating.

Myopia is a very significant and important problem now a days in modernised way of life style, where visual display units (VDU) have become a very important part of urban life. This condition is not only significant because of its high prevalence but it also plays a very important role for the visual morbidity and increases the risk for many vision threatening pathology like retinal detachment, glaucoma and ultimately blindness.

Epidemiological picture of myopia

A very significant number of infants are becoming myopic when they have been examined without any cycloplegic agents.^[3, 4] But it is seen that in premature infants the prevalence of myopia is significantly high.^[5, 6] In young adults and school going children the prevalence of myopia increases, almost 20-25% has been seen in mid to late teenage age groups, highest being almost 25- 35% in young adults of developed countries like USA.^[7-15] The report is also in support regarding the prevalence in Asia as well.^[16] This percentage decreases after the age of 45years and henceforth more regression has been seen over the age of 65years.^[17]

Aetiology of myopia^[18]

Types of myopia	Most probable aetiologies
Simple myopia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mostly unknown • Hereditary • Sufficient amount of close work
Nocturnal Myopia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Significant levels of dark focus of Accommodation
Pseudomyopia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Accomodative disorder • High exophoria • Cholinergic agonist agents
Degenerative myopia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inheritance • Retinopathy of prematurity • Interruption of light passing through ocular media • Unknown
Induced myopia	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Age related nuclear cataracts • Exposure to sulphonamides and other pharmaceutical agents • Significant variability in blood sugar level

Clinical manifestations of myopia

The most common feature of uncorrected myopia is distance blur vision. If somehow asthenopia is associated with myopia, it's due to some other cause like astigmatism, anisometropia, any vergence or accommodative disorder. Most of the school children complain that they cannot read the blackboard. Reduced unaided visual acuity is the first and foremost sign of myopia. If patients are able to adjust near working distance to coincide with the linear reciprocal of the dioptric amount of the refractive error, then the near vision may be "normal". Astigmatism is a very common refractive disorder which is mostly associated with myopia.

Probable treatment available for myopia

Till now there is no availability of universally accepted method for the prevention purpose of myopia. Optical correction in the form of spectacles or contact lenses help to give clear distance vision. Daily topical administration of atropine^[19-22] and cyclopenotolate^[22] help to reduce myopia progression rates in cases of children who have youth – onset myopia. But in addition to this, prolong application of atropine may show potential allergic adversities, idiosyncratic reactions, systemic toxicity^[23] and many adversities on retina.^[24] For the flattening purpose of the cornea and to reduce myopia, orthokeratology is a safe and effective procedure. Orthokeratology is the programmed fitting of a series of contact lenses for a period of weeks or months. Under refractive surgery Radial keratotomy (RK), photorefractive keratotomy (PRK), cryolathe keratomileusis, automatedlamellar keratomileusis (ALK) and

laser in situ keratomileusis (LASIK) are available, but they sufficiently increase the economic burden. So as a method of treatment, prevention along with the optometric aids, homoeopathic medicines can prove to have a wide scope in this radius of refractive error control like in cases of myopia, which can also be quite a cost effective option.

In the present study of myopia, no organ specific remedies have been chosen, i.e. on eye specific medicines. Here each and every patient was taken as a new and individual case, using the software named RADAR10.0 (No conflict of interest) and in that Boger Boenninghausen's Characteristic Repertory has been used for the selection of constitutional remedies.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Fig 1: Flow chart of the whole process of the study.

A request letter along with permission was taken from the principal of school of optometry, Bharati Vidyapeeth Deemed to be University, Pune, for the optometric guidance regarding the study. Prior permission from the principals of the schools, named Bharati Vidyapeeth Marathi Medium School for Girls' & Boys', Sarhad School, CBSE were taken for the screening process of the present study. Interns and Post graduate scholars of Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Medical College & Hospital participated in this study. The subjects were screened as per the symptoms, visual acuity test. Screened subjects were contacted over phone personally with the parents in case of minors for further optometric examination in the

department of optometry. A total no. of 50 patients fulfilled the inclusion criterias and were interested to participate in the study knowing all the details related to the study. In optometric examination, unaided visual acuity, pinhole visual acuity, visual acuity with present glass were taken. For the purpose of the dry retinoscopy, Heine Beta 200 retinoscope had been used. After that dry acceptance were being taken. The subjects having any other eye pathology except myopia and astigmatism were being excluded. Selected patients were registered in the O.P.D. of Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Hospital in the department of Repertory and case taking. All the cases were taken in a detailed format as per the case taking proforma, under the guidance of H.O.D. all the cases were properly analysed and with the help of RADAR10.0 (No conflict of interest) software and BBCR, the final prescription was done. No organ specific remedy has been chosen. The prescription was done based on the philosophy “patient as a whole”, not a particular part of it which is deranged. Each and every patient were given medicine of 1month duration along with instructions of consuming the medicines. In each visit patient were asked to fill up the Likert scale questionnaire for the evaluation purpose. Each patient were asked to visit once in a month keeping a gap of maximum 1months for the total 5 consecutive visits. In the Likert Scale mark has been assessed in the following way for each question:

- 1 – Poor
- 2 – Average
- 3 – Good
- 4 – Very good
- 5 - Excellent

Total evaluation was done under total score of 30.

- 26 – 30: Excellent
- 21 – 25: Very good
- 16 - 20: Good
- 11 – 15: Average
- 6-10: Poor

QUESTIONS	1	2	3	4	5
How do you feel in general regarding your health?					
How do you cope with stress?					
When you looking at a distance & then at a book-how well can you focus on the words quickly?					
With glasses/contact lenses?					
Without glasses/contact lenses?					
How well do you observe distant objects (Television)?					
With Glasses/contact lenses?					
Without glasses/contact lenses?					
How well do you observe near objects (Reading books)?					
With glasses/contact lenses?					
Without glasses/contact lenses?					
How well can you distinguish colour?					
With glasses/contact lenses?					
Without glasses/contact lenses?					

Fig 2: Likert scale questionnaire.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Female, 2. Male

Fig 3: Graphical presentation of gender distribution of the participant.

1. Low myopia
2. High myopia
3. Very high myopia

Fig 4: Graphical presentation of magnitude of myopia among the participants.

1. Arsenicum album; 2.Sulphur; 3.Natrum muriaticum;4.Natrum carbonicum
 5. Phosphorus; 6. Calcarea carbonica; 7.Pulsatilla nigricans

Fig 5: Medicinal distribution among the participants.

Fig 6: Bar diagram showing the age distribution.

Fig 7: Bar diagram comparing the likert scale score pre & post treatment.

The total age group was divided into four categories as 7-12years with a SD \pm 1.24, 13-18 years with a SD \pm 0.77, 19-24 years with a SD \pm 3.09 & 25-30years with a SD \pm 1.28. The results of the study has been analysed using the ANOVA test separately for right & left eye taking consideration of the spherical equivalent, the p value was 0.0002 of the right eye & 0.0010 for the left eye. The result of Likert scale score was being analysed with the paired t-test with a p value of 0.1969.

CONCLUSION

Though the study showed a statistically significant result but there is no significant clinical changes were observed. But Likert scale scoring has shown a very significant changes throughout the study. The patients also experienced so many improvement in their subjective symptoms. The study had a limited period of time. Further if we expand the duration of the study, it may show changes in the clinical domain.

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